

MODERN APPROACHES TO HIGHER EDUCATION QUALITY MANAGEMENT AND PROSPECTS FOR THEIR USE IN UZBEKISTAN

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At the present stage of development of New Uzbekistan, the sphere faces an important task: the preparation of highly educated citizens capable of active, creative activity in a free democratic society. In solving this issue, the development of creative principles in a person, the ability to transform the surrounding life, is of increasing importance. In this regard, the role of aesthetic, ethical education and upbringing increases. It is these directions that solve the issues of forming judgments, tastes, developing the inner emotional world and the spiritual image of the younger generation, serve to strengthen its consciousness, ideological conviction. The economic, social, political and cultural conditions of the life of modern society determine the task of actively introducing young people to the treasury of spiritual heritage, as well as world culture and universal values.

ABSTRACT

The article highlights the key changes in the education system of Uzbekistan and the main challenges facing the country in the coming years.

It is important to note that in our country special attention is paid to teachers. As the President said about this at the meeting: "We are a people striving for enlightenment, who have always revered and respected teachers. When I talk about a teacher, a mentor, I imagine the most respected and dear to me people, intelligent and modern, sincere and kind. After all, it was the teacher who taught us all and gave us education along with our dear parents. Today we are laying the foundation for a new era of Uzbekistan's development. In this process, our closest assistants are teachers and mentors, scientific and creative intelligentsia."

At the present stage of development, Uzbekistan faces strategic tasks, including the further development of the education system as the most important factor in the country's prosperity, sustainable economic growth, and employment.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of the higher education system" dated April 20, 2017 became a new impetus for a radical improvement in the sphere, a radical revision of the content of training at the level of international standards.

At the same time, the Program for the Comprehensive Development of the Higher Education System for the period 2017-2021 was approved, which includes measures to strengthen and modernize the material and technical base of universities, equip them with modern educational and scientific laboratories and modern information and communication technologies.

Today, higher education in Uzbekistan trains qualified specialists for various spheres of public life and sectors of the economy - scientific, economic, technical and others. The educational process systematizes knowledge and acquired skills, orienting students towards solving theoretical and practical problems in the vector of the chosen specialization with the creative use of the achievements of modern scientific thought and technology.

It should be noted that a group of international experts involved in the cooperation of UNESCO and the consulting company DGP Research & Consulting conducted a comprehensive study of the education system of Uzbekistan in January-June 2017. Based on the results of the analysis, proposals were developed on the need to further ensure the integrity of theory and practice, improve the mechanism for monitoring the quality of education, and develop effective cooperation with foreign universities.

One of the innovations in organizing the preparation and conduct of the process of admission to higher educational institutions for graduates of secondary schools, academic lyceums and professional colleges is the provision of the opportunity to enter several higher educational institutions simultaneously, the opening of evening and correspondence departments, faculties. The next important event in the country was the introduction of a system that allows universities to independently determine the admission of students to the first year, taking into account their real opportunities.

One of the main goals of reforming higher education is to ensure the real independence of universities in training and research activities. An important criterion for preventing the decline in the quality of higher education will be the availability of faculty with academic degrees.

The country has begun work on the creation of private universities and the opening of branches of leading universities in the development of the countries of the world, which will increase the opportunity for young people to receive higher education in selected areas. As a result, conditions will be created for the transformation of the country in the course of 10 years into the educational center of Central Asia for the training of highly qualified specialists.

This process puts forward the task of increasing the number of foreign students, which is of great importance in shaping the competitiveness of the higher education system and is important for popularizing the modern intellectual image of the country in the world community.

A comprehensive analysis of the work of higher educational institutions in modern conditions has revealed a number of existing problems that adversely affect the level and quality of training of highly qualified bachelors and masters:

- The national educational system has not adapted to the profound changes in society, which has led to limited access to higher education for certain citizens, low-income families, and the socially vulnerable part of the population. The under-coverage of the student-age population by the higher education system in Uzbekistan (about 20%) is low by regional and international standards. The global trend is to increase the number of students studying at universities.

- There is a shortage of qualified personnel in the republic for new sectors of the economy, business, entrepreneurship and joint ventures. This is especially true for such areas as space research, the nuclear industry, the information economy, heavy engineering, and the pharmaceutical industry.

- There is insufficient connection between universities and private business. According to a World Bank study, 35.0% of companies in Uzbekistan face difficulties in finding qualified specialists with higher education.

- The level of the material and technical base of individual universities does not meet modern requirements. The low level of use of information technologies in the educational process remains, both in terms of expanding access and in terms of using new teaching methods.

- Insufficiently high level of scientific potential of teachers working in higher education. In Uzbekistan, in the structure of the teaching staff, the share of

doctors of science (PhD , S with D) is only 37.9%, the remaining 62.1% are teachers who do not have academic degrees. The trend of recent years is the aging of scientific and pedagogical personnel with academic degrees and titles, while reducing the influx of young people. Teachers of pre-retirement and retirement age account for 31.3% of the total number of highly qualified specialists.

- There is an acute shortage of teachers with knowledge of foreign languages.

- Further improvement of the system for preparing doctors of sciences and the work of specialized councils for the defense of doctoral dissertations is required.

- Higher educational institutions need a systematic professional development of the teaching staff, including those in foreign universities.

- The system of distance learning for highly qualified personnel and postgraduate education remains underdeveloped in the republic.

Thus, as a conclusion, it should be noted that in Uzbekistan, over the years of a new stage of development, purposeful large-scale work has been carried out to reform the entire higher education system, which is extremely important in terms of developing innovative ideas, developing and implementing new technologies, as well as preparing graduates who meet the goals of the socio-economic development of the country.

Firstly, higher education is a fundamental component of human capital, competitive education is directly related to the reform processes in Uzbekistan. In this regard, the main direction is to stimulate research and innovation activities in the

field of higher education, which create conditions for the dynamic development of society and improve the quality of the process of training competitive personnel, broad involvement of gifted youth in universities, strengthening the scientific potential of higher educational and scientific institutions, which is the main factor in the innovative development of the country.

Second, high-quality higher education is directly related to productivity growth and overall economic development. Higher education, in particular, is extremely important in terms of developing innovative ideas, developing and implementing new technologies, as well as preparing graduates who meet the goals of the country's socio-economic development.

Thirdly, in the context of training new personnel for the new economy, it is necessary to introduce innovative ideas into the educational, educational, research activities of universities, which will serve to further deepen targeted large-scale work to reform the entire higher education system.

Fourthly, the expansion of the country's international cooperation, the increase in export potential, the production of competitive goods for the domestic and

foreign markets strongly dictates the further improvement of the training of qualified bachelors and masters. This process is directly related to the need to improve the international ranking of universities and scientific organizations in Uzbekistan.

Fifth, the involvement of gifted university graduates in science needs to be reconsidered. In order to create favorable conditions for attracting talented masters to scientific and pedagogical work, it is necessary to attract financial support from the private sector, government and international organizations.

Reforms in the field of higher education in Uzbekistan are being implemented in cooperation with many international organizations, including Erasmus + (European Union program), JICA (Japan International Cooperation Agency), KOICA (Korea International Cooperation Agency). As a result of the joint programs being implemented, hundreds of teachers and students of Uzbekistan have the opportunity to get acquainted with advanced international experience in the education system, acquire new knowledge and skills, and improve their skills in the world's leading universities.

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